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FACE RECOGNITION: A SURVEY

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ABSTRACT

Face Recognition plays a major role in Biometrics. Feature selection is a measure issue in face recognition. This paper proposes a survey on face recognition. There are many methods to extract face features. In some advanced methods it can be extracted faster in a single scan through the raw image and lie in a lower dimensional space, but still retaining facial information efficiently. The methods which are used to extract features are robust to low-resolution images. The method is a trainable system for selecting face features. After the feature selection procedure next procedure is matching for face recognition. The recognition accuracy is increased by advanced methods.

KEYWORDS

Face features, feature selection, local binary pattern.

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REFERENCES

- [1] R. Chellappa, C. L. Wilson, and S. Sirohey, 1995. [Human and Machine Recognition of Faces: A Survey](#), Proc.of the IEEE, vol.83, no.5, pp.705-740.
- [2] Robert J. Baron, 1981. [Mechanisms of Human Facial Recognition](#), International Journal of ManMachine Studies, vol.15, no.2, pp.137-178.
- [3] R. Brunelli and T. Poggio, 1993. [Face Recognition: Features versus Templates](#), IEEE Tran. on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence, vol.15, no.10, pp.1042-1052.
- [4] E. Osuna, R. Freund, and F. Girosi, 1997. [Training Support Vector Machines: An Application to Face Detection](#), In IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition, pp.193-199.
- [5] Vladimir N. Vapnik, 1995. [The Nature of Statistical Learning Theory](#)", Springer Verlag, Heidelberg, DE.
- [6] L. Sirovich and M. Kirby, 1987. [Low-dimensional Procedure for the Characterization of Human Faces](#), Journal of Optical Society of America, vol.4, no.3, pp.519-524.
- [7] Matthew Turk and Alex Paul Pentland,1991. Eigenfaces for Recognition, Journal of Cognitive Neuroscience, vol.3, no.1, pp.71-86.
- [8] Peter N. Belhumeur, Joao P. Hespanha, and David J. Kriegman, 1997. Eigenfaces vs. Fisherfaces: Recognition Using Class Specific Linear Projection, IEEE Tran. On Pattern Analysis and Machine
- [9] Bernhard Scholkopf, Alex J. Smola, and Andre Bernhard, 1998. [Non-linear Component Analysis as a Kernel Eigenvalue Problem](#), Neural Computation, vol.10, no.5, pp.1299-1319.
- [10] M. H. Yang,2002. Kernel Eigenfaces vs. Kernel Fisherfaces: [Face Recognition using Kernel Methods](#), In IEEE International Conference on Face and Gesture Recognition, pp.215-220, Washington.
- [11] A. Jonathan Howell and Hilary Buxton, 1995. [Invariance in Radial Basis Function Neural Networks in Human Face Classification](#), Neural Processing Letters, vol.2, no.3, pp.26- 30.
- [12] Steve Lawrence, C. Lee Giles, Ah Chung Tsoi, and Andrew D. Back, 1998. [Face Recognition: A Convexional Neural Network Approach](#), IEEE Trans. on Neural Networks, vol.8, no.1, pp.98-113.
- [13] T. Poggio and K. K. Sung, 1994. [Example-based Learning for View-based Human Face Detection](#), ARPA Image Understanding Workshop.
- [14] M. J. Er, S. Wu, and J. Lu,1999. [Face Recognition using Radial Basis Function \(RBF\) Neural Networks](#), In 38th Conference on Decision & Control, Phoenix, Arizona USA, pp.2162-2167.
- [15] C. E. Thomaz, R. Q. Feitosa, and A. Veiga, 1998. [Design of Radial Basis Function Network as Classifier in face Recognition using Eigenfaces](#), In V th Brazilian Symposium on Neural Networks,pp.118-123.
- [16] Y. Yoshitomi, T. Miyaura, S. Tomito, and S. Kimura, 1997. [Face Identification using Thermal Image Processing](#), In IEEE InternationalWorkshop on Robot and Human Communication, pp.374-379.
- [17] Z. Liposcak and S. Loncaric, 1999. [Face Recognition from Profiles using Morphological](#)

- [Operations](#), In [International Workshop on Recognition](#), Analysis, and Tracking of faces and Gestures in RealTime Systems, pp.47-52.
- [18] Andreas Lanitis, Christopher J. Taylor, and Timothy Francis Cootes, 1997. [Automatic Interpretation and Coding of Face Images using Flexible Models](#), IEEE Tran. On Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence, vol.19, no.7, pp.743-756.
- [19] Alan L. Yuille,1991. [Deformable Templates for Face Recognition](#), Journal of Cognitive Neuroscience, vol.3,no.1, pp.59-70.
- [20] P. Penev and J. Atick, 1996. [Local Feature Analysis: A General Statistical Theory for Object Representation](#), Network:Computation in Neural Systems, vol.7, pp.477-500.
- [21] B. Yegnanarayana, 1999. [Artificial Neural Networks](#), Prentice-Hall of India, New Delhi.
- [22] Simon Haykin, 1999. [Neural networks: A Comprehensive Foundation](#), Prentice-Hall International, New Jersey.
- [23] C. M. Bishop, 1995. [Neural Networks for Pattern Recognition](#), Oxford University Press Inc., New York.
- [24] R. J. Mammone, 1993. [Artificial Neural Networks for Speech and Vision](#), Chapman and Hall, Cambridge.
- [25] T. Kohonen, 1988. [Self-Organization and Associative Memory](#), Springer-Verlag, New York.
- [26] T. J. Stonham, 1984. Practical Face Recognition and Verification with WISARD, In Aspects of Face Processing, pp.426-441.
- [27] D. Demers and G. W. Cottrell, 1993. Non-linear Dimensionality Reduction, In Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems, pp.580-587.
- [28] S. Lawrence, C. L. Giles, A. C. Tsoi, and A. D. Back, 1997. Face Recognition: A Convolutional Neural Network Approach, IEEE Trans. on Neural Networks, vol.8, no.1, pp.98-112.
- [29] Y. Dai and Y. Nakano, 1998. [Recognition of Facial Images with Low Resolution using a Hopfield Memory Model](#), Pattern Recognition, vol.31, no.2, pp.159-167.
- [30] J. Weng, N. Ahuja, and T. S. Huang, 1995. [Learning Recognition Segmentation of 3-D Objects from 2-D Images](#), In Int. Workshop Face Gesture Recognition, Zurich, Switzerland.
- [31] G. W. Cottrell and M. K. Fleming, 1990. [Face Recognition using Unsupervised Feature Extraction](#), In Int. J. Conf. on Neural Networks, pp.322-325, Paris.
- [32] Vladimir N. Vapnik, 1995. [The Nature of Statistical Learning Theory](#), Springer Verlag, Heidelberg, DE.

CLASS D POWER AMPLIFIER FOR MEDICAL APPLICATION

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ABSTRACT

The objective of this research was to design a 2.4 GHz class AB Power Amplifier (PA), with 0.18um Semiconductor Manufacturing International Corporation (SMIC) CMOS technology by using Cadence software, for health care applications. The ultimate goal for such application is to minimize the trade-offs between performance and cost, and between performance and low power consumption design. This paper introduces the design of a 2.4GHz class D power amplifier which consists of two stage amplifiers. This power amplifier can transmit 15dBm output power to a 50Ω load. The power added efficiency was 50% and the total power consumption was 90.4 mW. The performance of the power amplifier meets the specification requirements of the desired.

KEYWORDS

Two stage, Class D, Power amplifier, Healthcare

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REFERENCES

- [1] Stults BM., (1984) "[Preventive Health Care for the Elderly](#)", Western Journal of Medicine, pp 832-845.
- [2] Afsaneh Minaie, Ali Sanati-Mehrizy, Paymon Sanati-Mehrizy & Reza Sanati-Mehrizy (2013). "[Application of Wireless Sensor Networks in Health Care System](#)", ASEE, vol 3, pp 21-24.
- [3] Narayanunni, Vinay, Heng Gu, and Choongho Yu(2011) "[Monte Carlo simulation for investigating influence of junction and nanofiber properties on electrical conductivity of segregated-network nanocomposites.](#)" Acta Materialia 59.11 pp 4548-4555.
- [4] Gu, H., X-L. Gao, and X. C. Li(2009)"[Molecular Dynamics Study on Mechanical Properties and Interfacial Morphology of an Aluminum Matrix Nanocomposite Reinforced by -Silicon Carbide Nanoparticles.](#)" Journal of Computational and Theoretical Nanoscience 6.1 pp61-72.
- [5] Q Zhang, X Xiao, YT Cheng, MW Verbrugge (2014)"[A non-destructive method for measuring the mechanical properties of ultrathin films prepared by atomic layer deposition](#)", Applied Physics Letters 105 (6), 061901
- [6] X Yu, X Wang, Q Zhang, J Li, J Liu (2014) " [Oxidation-resistant, solution-processed plasmonic Ni nanochain-SiOx \(x< 2\) selective solar thermal absorbers,](#)" Journal of Applied Physics 116 (7), 073508.
- [7] H Liu, J Liu, Y Liu, K Bertoldi, CD Vecitis (2014) "Quantitative 2D electrooxidative carbon nanotube filter model: Insight into reactive sites", Carbon 80, pp 651-664.
- [8] Qinghua Wang, Huimin Xie, Jia Liu, Xue Feng, Fulong Dai(2009) " [Instability and failure analysis of film-substrate structure under electrical loading](#)" , International Conference on Electronic Packaging Technology & High Density Packaging, pp 1027-1029.
- [9] Liang Wang, Sajjad H. Marufa, Devid Manigliob, c, Yifu Ding (2012)" Fabrication and characterizations <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0008622314008604>of crosslinked porous polymer films with varying chemical compositions", Polymer ,Volume 53, Issue 17, pp 3749–3755.
- [10] Liang Wang, Yifu Ding (2015)"[Creating micro-structured hydrogel-forming polymer films by photopolymerization in an evaporating solvent: Compositional and morphological evolutions](#)", European Polymer Journal, Volume 66, pp 99–107.
- [11] Wei Cai , Leslie Lauren Gouveia, "[Modeling and simulation of Maximum power point tracker in Ptolemy](#)" , Journal of Clean Energy Technologies, Vol. 1, No. 1, 2013 , PP 6-9.
- [12] Wei Cai, Jeremy. Chan, David Garmire, "[3-Axes MEMS Hall-Effect Sensor,](#)" presented by the 2011 IEEE Sensors Applications Symposium, pp141-144.
- [13] Wei Cai, Xuelin Cui, Xiangrong Zhou, "[Optimization of a GPU Implementation of Multidimensional RF Pulse Design Algorithm,](#)" International Conference on Bioinformatics and Biomedical Engineering 2011
- [14] Wei Cai & Frank Shi, (2016) "[2.4 GHz Heterodyne Receiver for Healthcare Application](#)", IJPPS, vol 6,pp 1-7.

- [15] Bo Shi, Michael Yan Wah Chia (2011) “[On The Performance of Class-D Power Amplifiers With RF Pulse-Width Modulation](#)”, Proceedings of the Asia-Pacific Microwave Conference, pp1550-1553.
- [16] Jianhui Cui, Ke Zhang, Tong Tian (2013)“[A Dual-Level and Dual-Band Class-D CMOS Power Amplifier for IoT Applications](#)”, IEEE 11th International New Circuits and Systems Conference.

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SECURITY THREATS ON CLOUD COMPUTING VULNERABILITIES

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ABSTRACT

Clouds provide a powerful computing platform that enables individuals and organizations to perform variety levels of tasks such as: use of online storage space, adoption of business applications, development of customized computer software, and creation of a “realistic” network environment. In previous years, the number of people using cloud services has dramatically increased and lots of data has been stored in cloud computing environments. In the meantime, data breaches to cloud services are also increasing every year due to hackers who are always trying to exploit the security vulnerabilities of the architecture of cloud. In this paper, three cloud service models were compared; cloud security risks and threats were investigated based on the nature of the cloud service models. Real world cloud attacks were included to demonstrate the techniques that hackers used against cloud computing systems. In addition, countermeasures to cloud security breaches are presented.

KEYWORDS

Cloud computing, cloud security threats and countermeasures, cloud service models

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REFERENCES

1. DataLossDB Open Security Foundation. <http://datalosddb.org/statistics>
2. Sophos Security Threat Report 2012. <http://www.sophos.com/>
3. Amazon.com Server Said to Have Been Used in Sony Attack, May 2011. <http://www.bloomberg.com/news/2011-05-13/sony-network-said-to-have-been-invaded-by-hackersusing-amazon-com-server.html>
4. D. Jamil and H. Zaki, "[Security Issues in Cloud Computing and Countermeasures](#)," International Journal of Engineering Science and Technology, Vol. 3 No. 4, pp. 2672-2676, April 2011.
5. K. Zunnurhain and S. Vrbsky, "[Security Attacks and Solutions in Clouds](#)," 2nd IEEE International Conference on Cloud Computing Technology and Science, Indianapolis, December 2010.
6. W. A. Jansen, "Cloud Hooks: Security and Privacy Issues in Cloud Computing," 44th Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences, pp. 1–10, Koloa, Hawaii, January 2011.
7. T. Roth, "[Breaking Encryptions Using GPU Accelerated Cloud Instances](#)," Black Hat Technical Security Conference, 2011.
8. CERT Coordination Center, Denial of Service. http://www.packetstormsecurity.org/distributed/denial_of_service.html
9. M. Jensen, J. Schwenk, N. Gruschka, and L. L. Iacono, "[On Technical Security Issues in Cloud Computing](#)," IEEE International Conference in Cloud Computing, pp. 109-116, Bangalore, 2009.
10. Thunder in the Cloud: \$6 Cloud-Based Denial-of-Service Attack, August 2010. http://blogs.computerworld.com/16708/thunder_in_the_cloud_6_cloud_based_denial_of_service_attack
11. DDoS Attack Rains Down on Amazon Cloud, October 2009. http://www.theregister.co.uk/2009/10/05/amazon_bitbucket_outage/
12. 2011 CyberSecurity Watch Survey, CERT Coordination Center at Carnegie Mellon University.
13. D. Catteddu and G. Hogben, "[Cloud Computing Benefits, Risks and Recommendations for Information Security](#)," The European Network and Information Security Agency (ENISA), November 2009.

14. Insider Threats Related to Cloud Computing, CERT, July 2012. <http://www.cert.org/>
15. Data Breach Trends & Stats, Symantec, 2012. <http://www.indefenseofdata.com/data-breach-trendsstats/>
16. 2012 Has Delivered Her First Giant Data Breach, January 2012. <http://www.infosecisland.com/blogview/19432-2012-Has-Delivered-Her-First-Giant-DataBreach.html>
17. A Few Wrinkles Are Etching Facebook, Other Social Sites, USA Today, 2011. http://www.usatoday.com/printedition/life/20090115/socialnetworking15_st.art.html
18. An Update on LinkedIn Member Passwords Compromised, LinkedIn Blog, June, 2012. <http://blog.linkedin.com/2012/06/06/linkedin-member-passwords-compromised/>
19. Dropbox: Yes, We Were Hacked, August 2012. <http://gigaom.com/cloud/dropbox-yes-we-werehacked/>
20. Web Based Attacks, Symantec White Paper, February 2009.
21. Symantec Internet Security Threat Report, 2011 Trends, Vol. 17, April 2012.
22. P. P. Ramgonda and R. R. Mudholkar, "[Cloud Market Cogitation and Techniques to Averting SQL Injection for University Cloud](#)," International Journal of Computer Technology and Applications, Vol. 3, No. 3, pp. 1217-1224, January, 2012.
23. A. S. Choudhary and M. L. Dhore, "[CIDT: Detection of Malicious Code Injection Attacks on Web Application](#)," International Journal of Computer Applications, Vol. 52, No. 2, pp. 19-26, August 2012.
24. Web Application Attack Report For The Second Quarter of 2012. <http://www.firehost.com/company/newsroom/web-application-attack-report-second-quarter-2012>
25. Visitors to Sony PlayStation Website at Risk of Malware Infection, July 2008. <http://www.sophos.com/en-us/press-office/press-releases/2008/07/playstation.aspx>
26. N. Provos, M. A. Rajab, and P. Mavrommatis, "Cybercrime 2.0: When the Cloud Turns Dark," ACM Communications, Vol. 52, No. 4, pp. 42–47, 2009.
27. S. S. Rajan, Cloud Security Series | SQL Injection and SaaS, Cloud Computing Journal, November 2010.

28. Researchers Demo Cloud Security Issue With Amazon AWS Attack, October 2011. http://www.pcworld.idg.com.au/article/405419/researchers_demo_cloud_security_issue_amazon_aws_attack/
29. M. McIntosh and P. Austel, "XML Signature Element Wrapping Attacks and Countermeasures," 2005 workshop on Secure web services, ACM Press, New York, NY, pp. 20–27, 2005.
30. N. Gruschka and L. L. Iacono, "[Vulnerable Cloud: SOAP Message Security Validation Revisited](#)," IEEE International Conference on Web Services, Los Angeles, 2009.
31. A. Tripathi and A. Mishra, "Cloud Computing Security Considerations Interface," 2011 IEEE International Conference on Signal Processing, Communications and Computing, Xi'an, China, September 2011.
32. H. C. Li, P. H. Liang, J. M. Yang, and S. J. Chen, "Analysis on Cloud-Based Security Vulnerability Assessment," IEEE International Conference on E-Business Engineering, pp.490-494, November 2010.
33. Amazon: Hey Spammers, Get Off My Cloud!
http://voices.washingtonpost.com/securityfix/2008/07/amazon_hey_spammers_get_off_my.html
34. W. Jansen and T. Grance, "Guidelines on Security and Privacy in Public Cloud Computing," Computer Security Division, Information Technology Laboratory, National Institute of Standards and Technology, Special Publication 800-144, December 2011.
35. Tackling the Insider Threat <http://www.bankinfosecurity.com/blogs.php?postID=140>
36. "Cloud Security Risks and Solutions," White Paper, BalaBit IT Security, July 2010.
37. S. J. Stolfo, M. B. Salem, and A. D. Keromytis, "Fog computing: Mitigating Insider Data Theft Attacks in the Cloud," IEEE Symposium on Security and Privacy Workshops, pp. 125-128, San Francisco, CA, 2012.
38. M. Jensen, C. Meyer, J. Somorovsky, and J. Schwenk, "On the Effectiveness of XML Schema Validation for Countering XML Signature Wrapping Attacks," First International Workshop on Securing Services on the Cloud, Milan, Italy, September 2011.
39. S. Gajek, M. Jensen, L. Liao, and J. Schwenk, "Analysis of Signature Wrapping Attacks and Countermeasures," IEEE International Conference on Web Services, pp. 575–582, Miami, Florida, July 2009.

**MODELLING OF NTC THERMISTOR USING ARTIFICIAL
NEURAL NETWORK FOR NONLINEARITY COMPENSATION**

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ABSTRACT

This paper investigates modelling of NTC thermistors using Steinhart-Hart equation for generic model generation and then parsing the same through the linearization algorithm based on Levenberg–Marquart back propagation technique with sigmoid activation function. The entire modelling and scripting of the linearization algorithm has been accomplished in the MATLAB paradigm. The results showcase small linearity error optimal in the chebyshev norms. The reported technique has a potential for linearization of other impedance based non-linear sensors as well. Further work is in progress to integrate the algorithm as a soft IP core in a full custom or semi-custom ASIC wherein thermistors are employed as sensors.

KEYWORDS

ANN, Levenberg–Marquart, Linearization techniques, MATLAB, Thermistors

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REFERENCES

- [1] Kamat, R.K. and Naik, G.M., (2002)“ Thermistors – In search of new applications, manufacturers cultivate advance NTC techniques”, *Sensor Review, An international journal of sensors and systems, U.K.*, Vol. 22, No.4, pp. 334-340
- [2] Kamat R.K., “Development of High Performance NTC Thermistors”, Ph.D. Thesis, Goa University (2003)
- [3] R.K. Kamat, G.M. Naik and V.M.S.Verenka, (2001), “Synthesis and Characterization of Nickel Manganese Carboxylate Precursors for Thermistor Applications”, *Texas Instrument’s Analog Application Journal, USA, Volume: 2001:1Q (First Quarter)*, pp. 52-55.
- [4] R.K. Kamat and G.M. Naik, Analogue to Digital Converter With Non-linear Transfer Function for Thermistor Applications, *Proceedings of International Measurement Confederation*, Retrieved from <http://www.imeko.org/publications/tc4-2002/IMEKO-TC4-2002-049.pdf>
- [5] Andrew J. Skinner and Martin F. Lambert, Log-Antilog Analog Control Circuit for Constant-Power Warm-Thermistor Sensors—Application to Plant Water Status Measurement, *IEEE SENSORS JOURNAL, VOL. 9, NO. 9, SEPTEMBER 2009*, pp 1049-1057
- [6] Deshmukh, M.D. and Panditrao, A., Design and development of thermistor based sensor for spirometry, *IEEE Electrical, Electronics and Computer Science (SCEECS), 2012 IEEE* , March 2012
- [7] Zvezditz P. Nenova and Toshko G. Nenov, Linearization Circuit of the Thermistor Connection, *IEEE TRANSACTIONS ON INSTRUMENTATION AND MEASUREMENT, VOL. 58, NO. 2, FEBRUARY 2009*
- [8] M. Diamond, “Linearization of resistance thermometers and other transducers,” *Rev. Sci. Instrum.*, vol. 41, no. 1, pp. 53–60, Jan. 1970.
- [9] Burke, “Linearizing thermistors with a single resistor, *Electron*” vol. 54, no. 11, pp. 151–154, 1981
- [10] Khan and R. Sengupta, “A linear temperature/voltage converter using thermistor in logarithmic network,” *IEEE Trans. Instrum. Meas.*, vol. IM-33, no. 1, pp. 2–4, Mar. 1984.
- [11] Khan, “An improved linear temperature/voltage converter using thermistor in logarithmic network,” *IEEE Trans. Instrum. Meas.*, vol. IM-34, no. 5, pp. 635–638, Dec. 1985.
- [12] D. Patranabis, S. Ghosh, and C. Bakshi, “Linearizing transducer characteristics,” *IEEE Trans. Instrum. Meas.*, vol. 37, no. 1, pp. 66–69, Mar. 1988.
- [13] D. K. Stankovic, “Linearized thermistor multivibrator bridges for temperature measurement,” *IEEE Trans. Instrum. Meas.*, vol. IM-23, no. 2, pp. 179–180, Jun. 1974.
- [14] D. Stankovic and J. Elazar, “Thermistor multivibrator as the temperature-to-frequency converter and as a bridge for temperature measurement,” *IEEE Trans. Instrum. Meas.*, vol. IM-26, no. 1, pp. 41–46, Mar. 1977.
- [15] Sundvist, “Simple, wide-range, linear temperature-to-frequency converters using standard thermistors,” *J. Phys. E, Sci. Instrum.*, vol. 16, no. 4, pp. 261–264, Apr. 1983.

- [16] R. N. Sengupta, "A widely linear temperature to frequency converter using a thermistor in a pulse generator," IEEE Trans. Instrum. Meas., vol. 37, no. 1, pp. 62–65, Mar. 1988.
- [17] S. Natarajan and B. B. Bhattacharyya, "Temperature-to-time converters," IEEE Trans. Instrum. Meas., vol. IM-26, no. 1, pp. 77–79, Mar. 1977.
- [18] W. T. Bolk, "A general digital linearizing method for transducers," J. Phys. E, Sci. Instrum., vol. 18, pp. 61–64, 1985. [19] W. Balzer, "Sensorkennlinien linearisieren," Feinwerktechnik und Messtechnik, no. 6, pp. 221–226, 1992
- [20] Flammini, D. Marioli, and A. Taroni, "Application of an optimal lookup table to sensor data processing," IEEE Trans. Instrum. Meas., vol. 48, no. 4, pp. 813–816, Aug. 1999.
- [21] Chin-Fu Tsai , Lung-Tsai Li ; Chin-Hao Li ; Ming-Shing Young, Implementation of Thermistor Linearization Using LabVIEW, IEEE Conference on Intelligent Information Hiding and Multimedia Signal Processing, 2009.
- [22] Sonowal, D. and Bhuyan, M. FPGA implementation of neural network for linearization of thermistor characteristics, IEEE Conference on Devices, Circuits and Systems (ICDCS), 2012, March 2012.

LOW POWER SI CLASS E POWER AMPLIFIER AND RF SWITCH FOR HEALTH CARE

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ABSTRACT

This research was to design a 2.4 GHz class E Power Amplifier (PA) for health care, with 0.18um Semiconductor Manufacturing International Corporation CMOS technology by using Cadence software. And also RF switch was designed at cadence software with power Jazz 180nm SOI process. The ultimate goal for such application is to reach high performance and low cost, and between high performance and low power consumption design. This paper introduces the design of a 2.4GHz class E power amplifier and RF switch design. PA consists of cascade stage with negative capacitance. This power amplifier can transmit 16dBm output power to a 50Ω load. The performance of the power amplifier and switch meet the specification requirements of the desired.

KEYWORDS

Cascode, Negative Capacitance, Class E, Power amplifier, Healthcare, RF switch

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REFERENCES

- [1] Stults BM., (1984) "Preventive Health Care for the Elderly", *Western Journal of Medicine*, pp 832- 845.
- [2] Afsaneh Minaie, Ali Sanati-Mehrizy, Paymon Sanati-Mehrizy & Reza Sanati-Mehrizy (2013). "Application of Wireless Sensor Networks in Health Care System", *ASEE*, vol 3, pp 21-24.
- [3] Ann K Nowinski, Fang Sun, Andrew D White, Andrew J Keefe & Shaoyi Jiang,(2012) "Sequence, structure, and function of peptide self-assembled monolayers", *Journal of the American Chemical Society*, Vol.134, Issue 13, pp 6000-6005.
- [4] Andrew David White, Ann Kasia Nowinski, Wenjun Huang, Andrew Keefe, Fang Sun & Shaoyi Jiang, (2012) "Decoding nonspecific interactions from nature", *Chemical Science*, Issue 12, pp3488-3494.
- [5] Jinjun Zhang, Bonsung Koo, Nithya Subramanian, Yingtao Liu & Aditi Chattopadhyay, (2015) "An optimized cross-linked network model to simulate the linear elastic material response of a smart polymer", *Journal of Intelligent Material Systems and Structures*.
- [6] Jinjun Zhang, Bonsung Koo, Yingtao Liu, Jin Zou, Aditi Chattopadhyay & Lenore Dai, (2015) "A novel statistical spring-bead based network model for self-sensing smart polymer materials." *Smart Materials and Structures*, Volume 24, Issue 8.
- [7] Jinjun Zhang, Kuang Liu, Chuntao Luo & Aditi Chattopadhyay, (2013) "Crack initiation and fatigue life prediction on aluminum lug joints using statistical volume element-based multiscale modeling", *Journal of Intelligent Material Systems and Structures* volume 24, Issue 17 pp 2097-2109.
- [8] Jinjun Zhang, J. Johnston & Aditi Chattopadhyay, (2014) "Physics-based multiscale damage criterion for fatigue crack prediction in aluminium alloy", *Fatigue & Fracture of Engineering Materials & Structures*, volume 37, issue 2, pp119-131.
- [9] JiaoJiao Wang, AB Phillion & GuiMin Lu, (2015) "Development of a visco-plastic constitutive modeling for thixoforming of AA6061 in semi-solid state", *Journal of Alloys and Compounds*, volume 609, pp 290-295
- [10] JiaoJiao Wang, D Brabazon, AB Phillion & GuiMin Lu, (2015) "An innovative two-stage reheating process for wrought aluminum alloy during thixoforming", *Metallurgical and Materials Transactions A*, Volume 46, Issue 9, pp 4191-4201
- [11] Jiaojiao Wang, Shuzhen Shang, Guimin Lu & Jianguo Yu, (2013) "Viscosity estimation of semisolid alloys based on thermal simulation compression tests", *International Journal of Materials Research*, Volume 104, Issue 3, , pp 255-259
- [12] Jiao Jiao Wang, Zhong Min Zhang, AB Phillion, Shu Zhen Shang & Gui Min Lu, (2016) "Alloy development and reheating process exploration of Al-Si casting alloys with globular grains for thixoforming", *J. Mater. Res.*
- [13] Gang Wang, Jingxian Wu, Guoqing Zhou & Geoffrey Ye Li, (2013) "Collision-tolerant media access control for asynchronous users over frequency-selective channels," *IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications*, vol. 12, no. 10, pp 5162-5171.
- [14] Gang Wang, Jingxian Wu & Yahong Rosa Zheng, (2014) "Optimum energy and spectral efficient transmissions for delay-constrained hybrid ARQ systems," *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology*.

- [15] Cheng Li & Paul Ampadu, (2015) "Energy-efficient NoC with variable channel width", IEEE 58th International Midwest Symposium on Circuits and Systems (MWSCAS).
- [16] Cheng Li & Paul Ampadu, (2015) "A compact low-power eDRAM-based NoC buffer", IEEE/ACM International Symposium on Low Power Electronics and Design (ISLPED), pp 116-121
- [17] Liangliang Zhang, Yuzheng Guo, Vinayak Vishwanath Hassan, Kechao Tang, Majeed A. Foad, Joseph C. Woicik, Piero A. Pianetta, John Robertson & Paul C McIntyre, (2016) "Interface Engineering for Atomic Layer Deposited Alumina Gate Dielectric on SiGe Substrates", ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces, Volume 8, Issue 29, pp 19110-19118.
- [18] Liangliang Zhang, Huanglong Li, Yuzheng Guo, Kechao Tang & Paul C. McIntyre, (2015) "Selective Passivation of GeO₂/Ge Interface Defects in Atomic Layer Deposited High-k MOS Structures", in ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces, Volume 7, Issue 37, pp 20499–20506.
- [19] Pei Luo, Yunsi Fei, Xin Fang, A Adam Ding, David R Kaeli & Miriam Leeser, (2015) "SideChannel Analysis of MAC-Keccak Hardware Implementations", Proceedings of the Fourth Workshop on Hardware and Architectural Support for Security and Privacy.
- [20] Tushar Swamy, Neel Shah, Pei Luo, Yunsi Fei, David Kaeli, (2014) "Scalable and efficient implementation of correlation power analysis using graphics processing units (GPUs)", Proceedings of the Third Workshop on Hardware and Architectural Support for Security and Privacy.
- [21] Shaohui Wang & Bing Wei, (2015) "Multiplicative Zagreb indices of k-trees", Discrete Applied Mathematics 180, pp 168-175.
- [22] Chunxiang Wang, Shaohui Wang & Bing Wei, (2016) "Cacti with Extremal PI Index", Transactions on Combinatorics, Volume 5, Issue 4.
- [23] Jiaze He & Fuh-Gwo Yuan, (2015) "Damage Identification for Composite Structures using a Cross-Correlation Reverse-Time Migration Technique", Structural Health Monitoring, 14(6): pp 558-570.
- [24] Jiaze He & Fuh-Gwo Yuan, (2016) "Lamb wave-based subwavelength damage imaging using the DORT-MUSIC technique in metallic plates." Structural Health Monitoring, 15(1) pp 65–80.
- [25] Vinay Narayanunni, Heng Gu & Choongho Yu, (2011) "Monte Carlo Simulation for Investigating Influence of Junction and Nanofiber Properties on Electrical Conductivity of Segregated-network Nanocomposites"; Acta Materialia, Volume 59, Issue 11, pp 4548–4555.
- [26] Yihua Zhou, Walter Hu, Bei Peng & Yaling Liu, (2014) "Biomarker Binding on an Antibody Functionalized Biosensor Surface: The Influence of Surface Properties, Electric Field, and Coating Density", The Journal of Physical Chemistry C, pp14586-14594.
- [27] Ru-Ze Liang, Lihui Shi, Haoxiang Wang, Jiandong Meng, Jim Jing-Yan Wang, Qingquan Sun & Yi Gu, (2016) "Optimizing Top Precision Performance Measure of Content-Based Image Retrieval by Learning Similarity Function", 23st International Conference on Pattern Recognition.
- [28] Ru-Ze Liang, Wei Xie, Weizhi Li, Hongqi Wang, Jim Jing-Yan Wang, Lisa Taylor, (201) "A novel transfer learning method based on common space mapping and weighted domain matching", IEEE 28th International Conference on Tools with Artificial Intelligence (ICTAI)

- [29] Wei Cai & Leslie Lauren Gouveia, "Modeling and simulation of Maximum power point tracker in Ptolemy", Journal of Clean Energy Technologies, Vol. 1, No. 1, 2013 , PP 6-9.
- [30] Wei Cai, Jeremy. Chan & David Garmire, "3-Axes MEMS Hall-Effect Sensor," presented by the 2011 IEEE Sensors Applications Symposium, pp141-144.
- [31] Wei Cai, Xuelin Cui & Xiangrong Zhou, "Optimization of a GPU Implementation of Multidimensional RF Pulse Design Algorithm," International Conference on Bioinformatics and Biomedical Engineering 2011
- [32] Wei Cai & Frank Shi, (2016) "2.4 GHz Heterodyne Receiver for Healthcare Application", IJPPS, vol 6,pp 1-7.
- [33] Kunal Datta & Hossein Hashemi, (2014) "Performance Limits, Design and Implementation of mm-Wave SiGe HBTClass-E and Stacked Class-E Power Amplifiers," JSCC, vol 49, pp 2150-2171.
- [34] Wei Cai & Frank Shi, (2016) "High Performance SOI RF Switch for Healthcare Application",2016, International Journal of Enhanced Research in Science, Technology & Engineering, Volume 5, Issue 10, pp 23-28.
- [35] P .Manikandan & Ribu Mathew, (2012) "Design of CMOS Class-E Power Amplifier for WLAN and Bluetooth", ICDCS, pp 81-88,.
- [36] Wei cai, liang huang & Wujie Wen, "2.4GHZ Class AB Power Amplifier for Healthcare Application" International Journal of Biomedical Engineering and Science (IJBES), Vol. 3, No. 2, April 2016

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RESEARCH IN BIG DATA – AN OVERVIEW

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ABSTRACT

Big data is a prominent term which characterizes the improvement and availability of data in all three formats like structure, unstructured and semi formats. Structure data is located in a fixed field of a record or file and it is present in the relational data bases and spreadsheets whereas an unstructured data file includes text and multimedia contents. The primary objective of this big data concept is to describe the extreme volume of data sets i.e. both structured and unstructured. It is further defined with three “V” dimensions namely Volume, Velocity and Variety, and two more “V” also added i.e. Value and Veracity. Volume denotes the size of data, Velocity depends upon the speed of the data processing, Variety is described with the types of the data, Value which derives the business value and Veracity describes about the quality of the data and data understandability. Nowadays, big data has become unique and preferred research areas in the field of computer science. Many open research problems are available in big data and good solutions also been proposed by the researchers even though there is a need for development of many new techniques and algorithms for big data analysis in order to get optimal solutions. In this paper, a detailed study about big data, its basic concepts, history, applications, technique, research issues and tools are discussed.

KEYWORDS:

Big data, Technologies, Visualization, Classification, Clustering

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Volume Link : <http://aircse.org/journal/iej/current.html>

REFERENCES

1. Neelam Singh, Neha Garg, Varsha Mittal, Data – insights, motivation and challenges, Volume 4, Issue 12, December-2013, 2172, ISSN 2229-5518 2013.
2. Karthik Kambatlaa, Giorgos Kollias b, Vipin Kumar c, Ananth Gramaa, Trends in big data Analytics, (2014) 74 2561–2573
3. Francis X. "[On the Origin\(s\) and Development of the Term \Big Data](#)" _ Francis X., 2012
4. Venkata narasimha inukollu¹, sailaja arsi¹ and srinivasa rao ravuri³ Security issues associated with big data in cloud computing Vol.6, No.3, May 2014
5. Matzat¹, Ulf-Dietrich Reips^{2,3} 1 Eindhoven "Big Data" 2012, 7 (1), 1–5 ISSN 1662-5544
6. Hong Kong, Park Shatin, Mining Big Data: Current Status, and Forecast to the Future
7. Anil K. Jain Clustering Big Data, 2012
8. Daniel Keim Big-Data Visualization.
9. Hsinchun Chen Business Intelligence And Analytics: From Big Data To Big Impact AZ 85721, OH 45221-0211 U.S.A. Mack Robinson, GA 30302-4015.
10. Ibrahim Abaker Targio Hashema, n, Ibrar Yaqooba, Nor Badrul Anuara, Salimah Mokhtara, Abdullah Gania, Samee Ullah Khan b, The rise of "big data" on cloud computing: Review and open research issues. 2014
11. Edd Dumbill, Making Sense of Big Data
12. Silva Robak , prof. Z. Szafrana, Zielona Góra Uniwersytet Zielonogórski Research Problems Associated with Big Data Utilization in Logistics and Supply Chains Design and Management 2014 249 DOI: 10.15439/2014F472
13. C.L. Philip Chen , Chun-Yang Zhang Data-intensive applications, challenges, techniques and technologies: A survey on Big Data 275 (2014) 314–347
14. Chaitanya Baru,¹ Milind Bhandarkar,² Raghunath Nambiar,³ Meikel Poess,⁴ and Tilmann Rabl Survey of Recent Research Progress and Issues in Big Data 2013.
15. Tackling the Challenges of Big Data 2014.
16. Stephen Kaisleri_SW. Alberto Espinosa Big Data: Issues and Challenges Moving Forward Stephen Kaisleri_SW. Alberto Espinosa 013 46th Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences
17. Challenges and Opportunities with Big Data A community white paper developed by leading researchers across the United States 1819
18. Danyang Dua , Aihua Lia*, Survey on the Applications of Big Data in Chinese Real Estate Enterprise 1st International Conference on Data Science, 2014

19. Shilpa, Manjit Kaur challenges and issues during visualization of big data , International Journal For Technological Research In Engineering Volume 1, Issue 4, December - 2013 ISSN (Online) 2347 – 4718
20. <http://felinlovewithdata.com/research/the-role-of-algorithms-in-data-visualization>
21. <http://prosjekt.ffi.no/unik-4660/lectures04/chapters/Algorithms2.html>
22. <http://www.creativebloq.com/design-tools/data-visualization-712402>

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AN IMPROVED METHOD TO DETECT INTRUSION USING MACHINE LEARNING ALGORITHMS

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ABSTRACT

An intrusion detection system detects various malicious behaviors and abnormal activities that might harm security and trust of computer system. IDS operate either on host or network level via utilizing anomaly detection or misuse detection. Main problem is to correctly detect intruder attack against computer network. The key point of successful detection of intrusion is choice of proper features. To resolve the problems of IDS scheme this research work propose “an improved method to detect intrusion using machine learning algorithms”. In our paper we use KDDCUP 99 dataset to analyze efficiency of intrusion detection with different machine learning algorithms like Bayes, NaiveBayes, J48, J48Graft and Random forest. To identify network based IDS with KDDCUP 99 dataset, experimental results shows that the three algorithms J48, J48Graft and Random forest gives much better results than other machine learning algorithms. We use WEKA to check the accuracy of classified dataset via our proposed method. We have considered all the parameter for computation of result i.e. precision, recall, F – measure and ROC.

KEY WORDS:

IDS, KDDCUP 99, Machine learning, WEKA, Network Security, Precision, Recall

For More Details : <https://airconline.com/iej/V4N2/4216iej03.pdf>

Volume Link : <http://airccse.org/journal/iej/current.html>

REFERENCES

- [1] Sourcefire. Snort open source network intrusion prevention and detection system (ids/ips). <http://www.snort.org>.
- [2] Liao, Hung-Jen, Chun-Hung Richard Lin, Ying-Chi Lin, and Kuang-Yuan Tung. "Intrusion detection system: A comprehensive review." *Journal of Network and Computer Applications* 36, no. 1 (2013): 16-24.
- [3] Debar, Herve. "An introduction to intrusion-detection systems." *Proceedings of Connect 2000* (2000).
- [4] Liao, Hung-Jen, Chun-Hung Richard Lin, Ying-Chih Lin, and Kuang-Yuan Tung. "Intrusion detection system: A comprehensive review." *Journal of Network and Computer Applications* 36, no. 1 (2013): 16-24.
- [5] Jyothsna, V., VV Rama Prasad, and K. Munivara Prasad. "A review of anomaly based intrusion detection systems." *International Journal of Computer Applications* 28, no. 7 (2011): 26-35.
- [6] Bashah, Norbik, Idris Bharanidharan Shanmugam, and Abdul Manan Ahmed. "Hybrid intelligent intrusion detection system." *World Academy of Science, Engineering and Technology* 11 (2005): 23-26.
- [7] Ghosh, Anup K., Aaron Schwartzbard, and Michael Schatz. "Learning Program Behavior Profiles for Intrusion Detection." In *Workshop on Intrusion Detection and Network Monitoring*, vol. 51462. 1999.
- [8] Xia, Tao, Guangzhi Qu, Salim Hariri, and Mazin Yousef. "An efficient network intrusion detection method based on information theory and genetic algorithm." In *Performance, Computing, and Communications Conference, 2005. IPCCC 2005. 24th IEEE International*, pp. 11-17. IEEE, 2005.
- [9] Caulkins, Bruce D., Joochan Lee, and Morgan Wang. "A dynamic data mining technique for intrusion detection systems." In *Proceedings of the 43rd annual Southeast regional conference* Volume 2, pp. 148-153. ACM, 2005.
- [10] Gudadhe, Mrudula, Prakash Prasad, and Kapil Wankhade. "A new data mining based network intrusion detection model." In *Computer and Communication Technology (ICCCT), 2010 International Conference on*, pp. 731-735. IEEE, 2010.
- [11] Pan, Zhi-Song, Song-Can Chen, Gen-Bao Hu, and Dao-Qiang Zhang. "Hybrid neural network and C4. 5 for misuse detection." In *Machine Learning and Cybernetics, 2003 International Conference on*, vol. 4, pp. 2463-2467. IEEE, 2003.
- [12] Gaddam, Shekhar R., Vir V. Phoha, and Kiran S. Balagani. "K-means+ id3: A novel method for supervised anomaly detection by cascading k-means clustering and id3 decision tree learning methods." *Knowledge and Data Engineering, IEEE Transactions on* 19, no. 3 (2007): 345-354.
- [13] Yasami, Yasser, and Saadat Pour Mozaffari. "A novel unsupervised classification approach for

network anomaly detection by k-Means clustering and ID3 decision tree learning methods." *The Journal of Supercomputing* 53, no. 1 (2010): 231-245.

- [14] Platt, J.C. "Fast Training of Support Vector Machines using Sequential Minimal Optimization", *Advances in Kernel Methods: Support Vector Learning*, pp. 185-208, 1998.
- [15] Lin, Chun-Fu, and Sheng-De Wang. "Fuzzy support vector machines." *Neural Networks, IEEE Transactions on* 13, no. 2 (2002): 464-471.
- [16] Tang, Hao, and Liang-sheng Qu. "Fuzzy support vector machine with a new fuzzy membership function for pattern classification." In *Machine Learning and Cybernetics, 2008 International Conference on*, vol. 2, pp. 768-773. IEEE, 2008.
- [17] Kim, Dong Seong, Ha-Nam Nguyen, and Jong Sou Park. "Genetic algorithm to improve SVM based network intrusion detection system." In *Advanced Information Networking and Applications, 2005. AINA 2005. 19th International Conference on*, vol. 2, pp. 155-158. IEEE, 2005.
- [18] Khan, Latifur, Mamoun Awad, and Bhavani Thuraisingham. "A new intrusion detection system using support vector machines and hierarchical clustering." *The VLDB Journal—The International Journal on Very Large Data Bases* 16, no. 4 (2007): 507-521.
- [19] Guo, Jun, Norikazu Takahashi, and Wenxin Hu. "An efficient algorithm for multi-class support vector machines." In *Advanced Computer Theory and Engineering, 2008. ICACTE'08. International Conference on*, pp. 327-331. IEEE, 2008.
- [20] Li, Lei, and Ke-nan Zhao. "A new intrusion detection system based on rough set theory and fuzzy support vector machine." In *Intelligent Systems and Applications (ISA), 2011 3rd International Workshop on*, pp. 1-5. IEEE, 2011.
- [21] Mulay, Snehal, P. R. Devale, and G. V. Garje. "Decision tree based support vector machine for intrusion detection." In *Networking and Information Technology (ICNIT), 2010 International Conference on*, pp. 59-63. IEEE, 2010.
- [22] Chen, Huanhuan, Qiang Wang, and Yi Shen. "Decision tree support vector machine based on genetic algorithm for multi-class classification." *Systems Engineering and Electronics, Journal of* 22, no. 2 (2011): 322-326.
- [23] Yi, Yang, Jiansheng Wu, and Wei Xu. "Incremental SVM based on reserved set for network intrusion detection." *Expert Systems with Applications* 38, no. 6 (2011): 7698-7707.
- [24] Lu, Wei, and Issa Traore. "Detecting new forms of network intrusion using genetic programming." *Computational Intelligence* 20, no. 3 (2004): 475-494.
- [25] Mabu, S., Chen, C., Lu, N., Shimada, K. and Hirasawa, K. "An Intrusion-Detection Model Based on Fuzzy Class-Association-Rule Mining Using Genetic Network Programming", *IEEE Trans. on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics, Part C: Applications and Reviews*, Vol. 40, No 99, pp. 1-10, 2010
- [26] Khayam, Syed Ali, Ayesha Binte Ashfaq, and Hayder Radha. "Joint network-host based malware

detection using information-theoretic tools." *Journal in computer virology* 7, no. 2 (2011): 159-172.

[27] Roesch, Martin. "Snort: Lightweight Intrusion Detection for Networks." *InLISA*, vol. 99, no. 1, pp. 229-238. 1999.

[28] Cisco, I. O. S. "NetFlow." (2008).

[29] Rothberg, Michael S. "Disk drive for receiving setup data in a self monitoring analysis and reporting technology (SMART) command." U.S. Patent 6,895,500, issued May 17, 2005.

[30] Hall, Mark, Eibe Frank, Geoffrey Holmes, Bernhard Pfahringer, Peter Reutemann, and Ian H. Witten. "The WEKA data mining software: an update." *ACM SIGKDD explorations newsletter* 11, no. 1 (2009): 10-18.

[31] <http://kdd.ics.uci.edu/databases/kddcup99/kddcup99.html> [32] Wu, Su-Yun, and Ester Yen. "Data mining-based intrusion detectors." *Expert Systems with Applications* 36, no. 3 (2009): 5605-5612.

**THE LEFT AND RIGHT BLOCK POLE PLACEMENT COMPARISON
STUDY: APPLICATION TO FLIGHT DYNAMICS**

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ABSTRACT

It is known that if a linear-time-invariant MIMO system described by a state space equation has a number of states divisible by the number of inputs and it can be transformed to block controller form, we can design a state feedback controller using block pole placement technique by assigning a set of desired Block poles. These may be left or right block poles. The idea is to compare both in terms of system's response.

KEYWORDS

MIMO, Block Controller Form, State Feedback Controller, Block Pole Placement Technique, Left and/or Right Block Poles

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Volume Link : <http://aircse.org/journal/iej/current.html>

REFERENCES

- [1] Chia-Chi Tsui, "Robust Control System Design: Advanced State Space Techniques", Second Edition, Marcel Dekker, 2004.
- [2] Malika Yaici, KamelHariche, "On Eigenstructure Assignment Using Block Poles Placement" European Journal Of Control, May 2014.
- [3] Malika Yaici, KamelHariche, "On Solvents Of Matrix Polynomials" International Journal Of Modeling And Optimization, Vol. 4, No. 4, August 2014.
- [4] Katsuhiko Ogata, "Modern Control Engineering", Third Edition, Prentice Hall, 1997.
- [5] M.V. Cook, "Flight Dynamics Principles", Second Edition, Butterworth-Heinemann, 2007.
- [6] William L. Brogan, "Modern Control Theory", Third Edition, Prentice Hall, 1990.
- [7] K. Hariche And E. D. Denman" On Solvents And Lagrange Interpolating Λ -Matrices" Applied Mathematics And Computation 25321-332 (1988).
- [8] E. Periera, "On Solvents Of Matrix Polynomials" Appl. Numer. Math., Vol. 47, Pp. 197-208, 2003.
- [9] E. Periera, "Block Eigenvalues And Solution Of Differential Matrix Equation" Mathematical Notes, Miskolc, Vol. 4, No.1 (2003), Pp. 45-51.
- [10] F. R. Gantmacher, Theory Of Matrices, New York: Chelsea, 1960.
- [11] I. Gohberg, P. Lancaster, L. Rodman, Spectral Analysis Of Matrix Polynomials: I. Canonical Forms And Divisors, Linear Algebra Appl., 20, Pp. 1-44, 1978.
- [12] I. Gohberg, P. Lancaster, L. Rodman, Spectral Analysis Of Matrix Polynomials: II. The Resolvent Form And Spectral Divisors, Linear Algebra Appl. 21, 1978.
- [13] I. Gohberg, P. Lancaster, L. Rodman, Matrix Polynomials, Academic Press, 1982.
- [14] P.Lancaster, Lambda-Matrices And Vibrating Systems, New York, Pergamon Press, 1966.
- [15] P. Lancaster, M. Timenetski, "The Theory Of Matrices", 2nd Ed., Academic Press, 1985.
- [16] Leang S. Shieh, Y. T Tsay "Transformation Of Solvents And Spectral Factors Of Matrix Polynomials And Their Applications" Int J. Control. Vol. 34, Pp. 813-823, 1981.
- [17] William S. Levine, "Control System Advanced Methods" CRC Press ,2011.
- [18] Magdi S. Mahmoud And Yuanqing Xia, Applied Control Systems Design, Springer-Verlag London Limited 2012.
- [19] BelkacemBekhiti, A. Dahimene, B. Nail, K. Hariche, And A. Hamadouche, "On Block Roots Of Matrix Polynomials Based MIMO Control System Design", 4th International Conference On

Electrical Engineering ICEE Boumerdes , 2015.

- [20] B. C. Moore, "On The Flexibility Offered By State Feedback In Multivariable Systems Beyond Closed Loop Eigenvalue Assignment", IEEE Trans. Autom. Control, Vol AC-21, No.5, Pp. 689-692, 1976.
- [21] J. Lu, H. D. Chiang And J. S. Thorp, "Eigenstructure Assignment By Decentralized Feedback Control", IEEE Trans. Autom. Control, Vol. AC-38, No.4, Pp. 587-594, 1993.
- [22] T. Clarke, S. J. Griffin And J. Ensor, "Output Feedback Eigenstructure Assignment Using A New Reduced Orthogonality Condition", Int. J. Control, Vol. 76, No.4, Pp. 390-402, 2002.
- [23] O. Bachelier, J. Bosche And D. Mehdi, "On Pole Placement Via Eigenstructure Assignment Approach", IEEE Trans. Autom. Control, Vol. AC-51, No.9, Pp. 1554-1558, 2006.
- [24] A. Pomfret And T. Clarke, "An Extension To Output-Feedback Eigenstructure Assignment: Structuring Controllers By Exploiting Unused Design Freedom", Int. J. Control, Vol.82, No.2, Pp. 207-216, 2009.
- [25] A. N. Andry, E. Y. Shapiro And J. C. Chung, "Eigenstructure Assignment For Linear Systems", IEEE Trans. Aerosp. Electron.Syst., Vol. 19, No.5, Pp. 711-729, 1983.
- [26] K. M. Sobel And E.J. Lallman, "Eigenstructure Assignment For The Control Of Highly Augmented Aircraft", J. Of Guidance, Control, And Dynamics, Vol. 12, No.3, Pp. 18-324, 1989.
- [27] J. -F. Magni, "Multimodel Eigenstructure Assignment In Flight-Control Design", Aerosp. Sci. Technol., Vol.3, Pp. 141-151, 1999

CLASSIFIER SELECTION MODELS FOR INTRUSION DETECTION SYSTEM (IDS)

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ABSTRACT

Any abnormal activity can be assumed to be anomalies intrusion. In the literature several techniques and algorithms have been discussed for anomaly detection. In the most of cases true positive and false positive parameters have been used to compare their performance. However, depending upon the application a wrong true positive or wrong false positive may have severe detrimental effects. This necessitates inclusion of cost sensitive parameters in the performance. Moreover the most common testing dataset KDD-CUP-99 has huge size of data which intern require certain amount of pre-processing. Our work in this paper starts with enumerating the necessity of cost sensitive analysis with some real life examples. After discussing KDD-CUP-99 an approach is proposed for feature elimination and then features selection to reduce the number of more relevant features directly and size of KDD-CUP-99 indirectly. From the reported literature general methods for anomaly detection are selected which perform best for different types of attacks. These different classifiers are clubbed to form an ensemble. A cost opportunistic technique is suggested to allocate the relative weights to classifiers ensemble for generating the final result. The cost sensitivity of true positive and false positive results is done and a method is proposed to select the elements of cost sensitivity metrics for further improving the results to achieve the overall better performance. The impact on performance trade of due to incorporating the cost sensitivity is discussed.

KEYWORDS

Intrusion detection system (IDS), True positive (TP), False Positive(FP), Support Vector Machine (SVM).

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Volume Link : <http://aircse.org/journal/iej/current.html>

REFERENCES

- [1] MahbodTavallae, EbrahimBagheri, Wei Lu, and Ali A. Ghorbani” A Detailed Analysis of the KDD CUP 99 Data Set” Proceedings of the 2009 IEEE Symposium on Computational Intelligence in Security and Defense Applications (CISDA 2009).
- [2] Chebrolu, Srilatha, Ajith Abraham, and Johnson P.Thomas."Feature deduction and ensemble design of intrusion detection systems." Computers & Security24, no. 4 (2005): 295-307.
- [3] FarhadSoleimanianGharehchopogh, Neda Jabbari, ZeinabGhaffari Azar “Evaluation of Fuzzy KMeans And K-Means Clustering Algorithms In Intrusion Detection Systems” INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SCIENTIFIC & TECHNOLOGY RESEARCH VOLUME 1, ISSUE 11, DECEMBER 2012 pp 66-72.
- [4] John, G.H., Langley, P.:Estimating Continuous Distributions in Bayesian Classifiers. In: Proc. of the 11th Conf. on Uncertainty in Artificial Intelligence (1995).
- [5] M.Revathi and T.Ramesh” NETWORK INTRUSION DETECTION SYSTEM USING REDUCED DIMENSIONALITY” Indian Journal of Computer Science and Engineering (IJCS) Feb2011 PP 61- 67.
- [6] Mary Slocum ”Decision making using ID3” RivierAcadmic Journal, Vol 8, No 2, 2012.
- [7] Dewan Md. Farid, Jerome Darmont and Mohammad Zahidur Rahman” Attribute Weighting with Adaptive NBTree for Reducing False Positives in Intrusion Detection” International Journal of Computer Science and Information Security, Vol. 8, No. 1, 2010 PP 19-26.
- [8] Alma Husagic-Selman” Intrusion Detection System using Fuzzy Logic” SOUTHEAST EUROPE JOURNAL OF SOFT COMPUTING Vol 2 No 1 March 2013 PP 14-20.
- [9] Daniele Loiacono, Andrea Marelli, Pier Luca Lanzi” Support Vector Regression for Classifier Prediction” ACM GECCO’07, July 2007 pp 1806-1813.
- [10] VANTHIENEN, J., G.WETS & G. CHEN (1996) “Incorporating fuzziness in the classical decision table formalism”. International Journal of Intelligent Systems. Vol. 11 (11), pp. 879-891.
- [11] W.NorHaizan W. Mohamed, MohdNajibMohdSalleh, Abdul Halim Omar” A Comparative Study of Reduced Error Pruning Method in Decision Tree Algorithms” IEEE International Conference on Control System, Computing and Engineering, 23 - 25 Nov. 2012, Penang, Malaysia.
- [12] MsS.Vijayarani ,MsM.Muthulakshmi “Comparative Analysis of Bayes and Lazy Classification Algorithms” International Journal of Advanced Research in Computer and Communication Engineering Vol. 2, Issue 8, August 2013 pp 3118-3124.
- [13] PhyuThiHtun, KyawThetKhaing “Anomaly Intrusion Detection System using Random Forests and kNearest Neighbor” International Journal of P2P Network Trends and Technology Vol. 3, Issue 1, August 2012 pp 67-71.
- [14] Mia Louise Westerlund “Classification with Kohonen Self-Organizing Maps” Soft Computing, Haskoli Islands, April 24, 2005
- [15] GurselSerpen and Zhenning Gao “Complexity Analysis of Multilayer Perceptron Neural Network Embedded into a Wireless Sensor Network” Conference Organized by Missouri University of Science and Technology 2014- Philadelphia, PA Procedia Computer Science 36 (2014) pp 192 – 197.

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LOW COST PAGE QUALITY FACTORS TO DETECT WEB SPAM

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ABSTRACT

Web spam is a big challenge for quality of search engine results. It is very important for search engines to detect web spam accurately. In this paper we present 32 low cost quality factors to classify spam and ham pages on real time basis. These features can be divided in to three categories: (i) URL features, (ii) Content features, and (iii) Link features. We developed a classifier using Resilient Back-propagation learning algorithm of neural network and obtained good accuracy. This classifier can be applied to search engine results on real time because calculation of these features require very little CPU resources

KEYWORDS

Web Spam, Search Engine, Web Spam Detection, Spam Classifier, Neural Network

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REFERENCES

- [1] A.Ntoulas, M. Najork, M. Manasse, and D. Fetterly, "Detecting spam Web pages through content analysis," in Proceedings of the 15th International Conference on World Wide Web (WWW), pp. 83– 92, May 2006.
- [2] Zhu V., Wu G. and Yunfeg M., "Research and Analysis of Search Engine Optimization Factors Based on Reverse Engineering", Proc. 3rd International Conference on Multimedia Information Networking and Security, 225-228 (2011).
- [3] M.Erdelyi, A. Garzo, and A. A. Benczur. "Web spam classification: a few features worth more." In Proceedings of the 2011 Joint WICOW/AIRWeb Workshop on Web Quality, WebQuality'11, Hyderabad, India, 2011.
- [4] D.Wang, D. Irani, and C. Pu, "Evolutionary study of web spam: Webb spam corpus 2011 versus webb spam corpus 2006," in Proceedings of the 8th International Conference on Collaborative Computing: Networking, Applications and Work-sharing (CollaborateCom), Pittsburgh, PA, USA, October 2012, pp. 40–49.
- [5] K.Thomas, C. Grier, J. Ma, V. Paxson, and D. Song. "Design and evaluation of a real-time url spam filtering service." In Proceedings of the IEEE S&P, 2011.
- [6] Prieto, V. M., A´ lvarez, M., and Casheda, F. (2012). "Analysis and detection of web spam by means of web content". In Proceedings of the 5th Information Retrieval Facility Conference, IRFC '12.
- [7] Yang, H. C., & Lee, C. H., "Post-level spam detection for social bookmarking web sites." In Advances in Social Networks Analysis and Mining (ASONAM), 2011 international Conference on (pp. 180-185). IEEE.
- [8] B. Markines, C. Cattuto, and F. Menczer, "Social spam detection," in Proceedings of the 5th International Workshop on Adversarial Information Retrieval on the Web (AIRWeb), pp. 41–48, New York, NY, USA: ACM, 2009.
- [9] Wang F., Li Y. and Zhang Y., "An Empirical study on the Search Engine Optimization Technique and Its Outcomes" Proc. 2nd International Conference on AIMSEC, 2767-2770 (2011).
- [10] Y.-M. Wang, M. Ma, Y. Niu, and H. Chen, "Spam double-funnel: Connecting Web spammers with advertisers," in Proceedings of the 16th International Conference on World Wide Web (WWW), pp. 291–300, New York, NY, USA:ACM Press, 2007.
- [11] K. Chellapilla and A. Maykov, "A taxonomy of JavaScript redirection spam," in Proceedings of the 3rd International Workshop on Adversarial Information Retrieval on the Web, 2007.
- [12] E.Enge, "Matt cutts interviewed by eric enge," Article online at <http://www.stonetemple.com/articles/interview-matt-cutts-012510.shtml>, April 2010 [13] Martinez-Romo, J. and Araujo, "A. Web Spam Identification Through Language Model Analysis." AIRWeb. 2009..
- [14] M. J. Kleinberg, "Authoritative sources in a hyperlinked environment," Journal of the ACM, vol. 46, no. 5, pp. 604–632, 1999.
- [15] Patil Swati P., Pawar B.V. and Patil Ajay S., "Search Engine Optimization: A Study", Research Journal of Computer and Information Technology Sciences, Vol. 1(1), 10-13, February (2013).